

EVALUATION OF THE INTERFACIAL FRACTURE TOUGHNESS OF A CARBON FIBER REINFORCED THERMOPLASTIC COMPOSITE BY CYCLIC SINGLE-FIBER PUSH-OUT TESTS

Michael Greisel, Michael Schulz, Wolfgang M. Mueller, Judith Moosburger-Will and Siegfried Horn

Experimental Physics II, Institute of Physics, University of Augsburg
86153 Augsburg, Germany

Email: michael.greisel@physik.uni-augsburg.de,

web page: <http://www.physik.uni-augsburg.de/en/lehrstuehle/exp2>

Keywords: Single-fiber push-out test, interfacial fracture toughness, thermoplastic composite

ABSTRACT

Cyclic single-fiber push-out tests performed with a flat-end indenter tip of cylindrical shape have been conducted on an unidirectional carbon fiber reinforced polyetheretherketone composite to evaluate the interfacial fracture toughness. Since stable crack propagation along the interface region between fiber and matrix is the main energy dissipating process during push-out, the interfacial fracture toughness is the most suitable material parameter for a quantitative evaluation of the interfacial adhesion between fiber and matrix. The fracture toughness can be assessed by a modified single-fiber push-out test and a detailed energy analysis according to a recently published method. However, the investigated composite partially shows no clear indication of the crack reaching the backside of the test specimen in the force-displacement diagram due to a high frictional energy contribution arising from the slipping of the completely debonded fiber against the surrounding matrix. In the presented work, an expanded approach to quantify the relevant energy dissipated by stable crack propagation is proposed, which allows to determine the initiation of crack propagation as well as the end of crack growth. An additional push-back of the tested fibers supports the interpretation of the end of crack growth and the transition to friction in the original push-out experiment. The detailed energy analysis of push-out and push-back allows the determination of the crack energy dissipated during debonding of fiber and matrix and takes into account plastic deformation of the matrix and the work of friction. Since the mechanical performance of fiber reinforced composites is closely related to their interfacial properties, the presented method of back and forth slipping of the fiber is of high importance to investigate the interfacial adhesion between fiber and matrix in fiber reinforced composites with high interfacial friction.

1 INTRODUCTION

It is well recognized that the mechanical performance of fiber reinforced composites is closely related to the interfacial adhesion between fiber and matrix [1-3]. Since the fiber-matrix interface transfers mechanical load from matrix to fiber via mechanical interlocking, physical and chemical bonding or combinations of these, it is a key parameter in the conception of fiber reinforced composites in structural applications [2, 3]. In order to characterize the interfacial properties and to assess the interfacial debonding energy at the microscopic level, single-fiber pull-out, microbond, fragmentation and single-fiber push-out tests are currently used. Among these methods, the single-fiber push-out test has a high significance due to the investigation of real composites considering the presence of neighboring fibers, the local matrix morphology and inherently present stresses at the interface [4, 5].

Recently, Mueller et al. [6, 7] published a modification of the push-out loading scheme which enables a quantification of the energy dissipated during the debonding process of fiber and rigid ceramic matrix under compression loading of the fiber. Subsequently, this approach was expanded to more ductile matrix composites, e.g. carbon fiber reinforced polymers [8-10]. Using a cyclic loading schedule consisting of subsequent unloading-reloading cycles, the dissipative and non-dissipative energy contributions can be evaluated separately and the plastic matrix deformation as well as the work of

friction are taken into account. In addition, the occurrence of stable and unstable crack propagation is considered.

In the present publication, an extension of the method to quantify the relevant crack energy dissipated by stable crack growth in composite materials comprising a high interfacial friction contribution is presented. Additional push-back tests are conducted to support the determination of the crack energy. It seems that for the investigated polyetheretherketone (PEEK) composite the excess compressional deformation energy stored in the tested fiber is dissipated in interfacial friction. The friction contribution prevents an abrupt fiber relaxation towards the back side of the specimen when final debonding occurs. The presented push-out method of back and forth slipping of the fiber leads to a more reliable determination of the interfacial fracture toughness of composites with high interfacial friction between fiber and matrix.

2 EXPERIMENTAL

2.1 Material and sample preparation

The specimen investigated in the present study is an unidirectional carbon fiber reinforced thermoplastic composite consisting of HexTow[®] AS4 carbon fibers and PEEK matrix material (C/PEEK). The unidirectional laminate was manufactured by a heat pressing process using an adjusted heat treatment cycle with 15 minutes dwell time at 380 °C and 10 bar and heating and cooling rates of 4.5 to 8 K/min. A plate of dimension 300 mm x 300 mm x 2.0 mm (length x width x thickness) with unidirectional stacking of 14 tape layers was made.

For the push-out tests, thin slices of about 10 mm x 2.0 mm x 0.7 mm were cut by the diamond saw and thinned to an appropriate thickness by a two-sided lapping and polishing process (Precision Lapping and Polishing System PM5, Logitech Ltd.). Thus, plane-parallel sample surfaces were generated with minimal damage to the sample and with the fiber axis direction being parallel aligned to the thickness direction of the slices. According to this procedure, three push-out samples with different thicknesses were produced. An overview of the samples prepared is given in Table 1.

Sample	Specimen thickness (μm)
C/PEEK-01	22.6 ± 1.5
C/PEEK-02	35.7 ± 0.6
C/PEEK-03	52.2 ± 1.6

Table 1: Overview of C/PEEK samples investigated by single-fiber push-out testing.

In the next step, the thinned slices were placed on glass substrates with a groove of typically 50 μm in width. The setting by quartz wax ensured a close and stiff contact to the substrate.

2.2 Single-fiber push-out test

The single-fiber push-out tests were performed using an Universal Nanomechanical Tester (Asmec GmbH), which allows displacement-controlled measurements in normal direction with an accuracy of 0.01 mN and 1 nm, respectively. In lateral direction, the positioning accuracy of the indenter tip is 1 μm . In the present study, the push-out tests were performed with a flat-end indenter tip of cylindrical shape (diameter at the tip of 5.3 μm). The push-out tests were conducted using a cyclic loading schedule, published in recent push-out studies [8-10]. The cyclic loading schedule consists of subsequent unloading-reloading cycles in regular steps of 100 nm and 200 nm. The loading/ unloading segments were performed at a displacement rate of 50 nm/s up to a maximum indenter displacement of 6.0 μm . The individually tested fibers were chosen randomly irrespective of the local fiber volume content surrounding the measurement position. A number of at least 20 fibers of comparable cross-section area were tested for each push-out sample. Based on this random selection, the results are supposed to represent the interfacial properties and failure behavior of the whole sample.

2.3 Single-fiber push-back test

By turning over the samples and fixing by quartz wax above the groove, push-back tests can be conducted on the pre-pushed fibers. Since the protruding fibers are completely debonded after push-out testing, only frictional sliding and wear phenomena can be characterized. The cyclic loading schedule of the push-back tests is completely identical to the push-out testing.

2.4 Energy analysis

A recent energy analysis of single-fiber push-out tests of a SiC/SiC composite [6, 7] showed that the interfacial fracture toughness can be evaluated by adding unloading-reloading cycles to the loading schedule. This approach is expanded to ductile matrix composites, e.g. carbon fiber reinforced polymers [8-10]. The total energy is separated into dissipative and non-dissipative energy contributions during push-out testing. The non-dissipative energy corresponds to elastic deformation of fiber and matrix and is calculated by integration of the area below the unloading curve. The dissipative energy is composed of two contributions: The plastic deformation energy of fiber, matrix and interface (i.e. the crack energy) and the work of friction including the slipping of the fiber against the matrix in the debonded region and the effect of Poisson expansion of the fiber. All contributions are calculated by integration as a function of indenter displacement following the approach of Refs. [6-10].

The comprehensive consideration of the dissipative and non-dissipative energy contributions reveals a change in material response, which is interpreted as the initiation of crack growth [9, 10]. The point of complete fiber debonding, i.e. the end of crack growth, is indicated by a distinct signature in the load-displacement curves in our previous studies [9, 10]. After obtaining the energy dissipated in stable crack growth $\Delta E_{\text{crack,stable}}$, the interfacial fracture toughness $\langle G \rangle$ can be calculated according to Eq. (1)

$$\langle G \rangle = - \frac{\Delta E_{\text{crack,stable}}}{\Delta A_{\text{crack,stable}}} \quad (1)$$

The corresponding fracture surface area of stable crack growth $\Delta A_{\text{crack,stable}}$ is quantified according to a new approach presented in Refs. [7, 9], which includes the occurrence of stable and unstable crack growth. It is based on a quantification of the crack energy, normalized to the circumference of the tested fiber, as a function of the sample thickness, i.e. the length of the fibers. The linear relationship between the total energy dissipated during stable crack propagation and the sample thickness was verified experimentally [7, 9].

3 RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

3.1 Comparison of push-out behavior

During single-fiber push-out testing, the compression-loaded fiber is debonded from the surrounding matrix by the propagation of a mode II crack [4]. The energy stored elastically in the compressed fiber is released in unstable crack growth and leads to an abrupt relaxation of the fiber towards the back side of the specimen. This is indicated by a sudden load drop in the load-displacement curves and can be associated with complete debonding, as published in recent push-out studies [8, 9].

In Figure 1(a), a representative load-displacement diagram of a cyclic push-out test on the C/PEEK composite is presented. After a linear increase of the envelope curve up to an indenter displacement of about 0.5 μm , deviation from linear elastic behavior until peak load can be observed. After the maximum, the load decreases over several cycles followed by a sudden drop in load. This abrupt push-out behavior is obtained at almost half of the measurements performed. The other half of the number of push-out tests reveal the failure behavior shown in Figure 1(b). After peak load, the load decreases over a considerable larger displacement range ending in a nearly constant load range (around 15 mN). At this part of the experiment, the load-displacement curve is characterized by a zigzag trend around its maximum values, which is attributed to a stick-slip behavior along the interface. This progressive failure behavior is attributed to high interfacial friction. Thus, the excess elastic energy is released in work of friction during slipping of the debonded fiber against the ambient matrix.

The progressive push-out behavior is obtained independent of the specimen thickness, the fiber

diameter and the local fiber volume fraction surrounding the tested fiber. Thus, the nature and the morphology of the fiber-matrix interface itself seems to be responsible for the different failure behavior. Since there is no distinct signature in the load-displacement curves, which can be associated with complete debonding of fiber and matrix, an extended method is required to determine the relevant crack energy dissipated in stable crack propagation for the investigated C/PEEK composite material.

Figure 1: Load-displacement diagrams of cyclic single-fiber push-out tests on C/PEEK with abrupt (a) and progressive (b) push-out behavior.

3.2 Energy analysis of abrupt and progressive push-out behavior

The energy contribution $\Delta E_{\text{crack,stable}}$ can be determined by the modified push-out procedure and the detailed energy analysis described in Section 2.4. In Figure 2, the total dissipated plastic deformation energy $E_{\text{plastic,total}}$, which corresponds to the sum of the incremental plastic energy contributions per cycle, of an abrupt (Figure 2(a)) and a progressive (Figure 2(b)) push-out are presented as a function of the indenter displacement. The moderate increase of $E_{\text{plastic,total}}$ up to an indenter displacement of around $0.8 \mu\text{m}$ is attributed to plastic matrix deformation in both cases [9, 10]. Subsequently, the slopes of the curves approach a linear increase up to a displacement of around $3.1 \mu\text{m}$ and $2.9 \mu\text{m}$, respectively. This linear increase is associated with stable crack propagation [9, 10]. Back-extrapolation of the linear regression to zero dissipated plastic deformation energy yields the initiation of crack propagation (Figure 2, marked by gray square at around $0.8 \mu\text{m}$). This approach is applicable to both failure behaviors.

Figure 2: Total plastic energy dissipated during abrupt (a) and progressive (b) push-out process as a function of indenter displacement.

In case of abrupt push-out behavior, the point of complete fiber debonding, i.e. the end of crack growth, is indicated by a sudden drop in load in the load-displacement curves (see Figure 1(a)). Thus, the difference in energy between the last value of $E_{\text{plastic,total}}$ obtained and the value at crack initiation (both marked by gray squares, Figure 2(a)) yields $\Delta E_{\text{crack,stable}}$. In case of progressive failure, deviation from linear increase of $E_{\text{plastic,total}}$ at a displacement of around 2.9 μm can be observed. This deviation can be interpreted as the end of crack propagation and the transition to frictional sliding between debonded fiber and matrix. Additional push-back tests of the pushed fibers are performed to support this interpretation.

3.3 Cyclic single-fiber push-back tests

In Figure 3, typical load-displacement curves of cyclic single-fiber push-back tests performed on pre-pushed fibers are shown. During push-out testing, the fiber-matrix bonding either fails abruptly (Figure 3(a)) or progressively (Figure 3(b)), as described in Section 3.1. It can be seen that the push-back curves are strongly dominated by the stick-slip effect independent of the failure behavior during push-out testing. This oscillating trend is comparable to the load-displacement curve of a progressive push-out at a late stage of the experiment (see Figure 1(b)). The coincidence of the curve shapes of push-out and push-back confirms that the progressive failure is controlled by interfacial friction between fiber and matrix at the end of the push-out test. This friction contribution prevents an abrupt fiber relaxation towards the specimen back side at the moment of complete debonding. The observed zigzag-like decrease in maximum load per cycle of the push-back curves is attributed to abrasion processes along the sliding surfaces. Since the push-back tests show no difference between abrupt and progressive failure behavior during push-out, in both cases completely debonded fibers were tested. This supports the interpretation of a completely debonded fiber at the end of the linear increase of the total plastic energy dissipated during push-out testing. Thus, the deviation from linearity in case of progressive push-out can be regarded as the endpoint of stable crack propagation in the energy analysis of cyclic single-fiber push-out testing.

Figure 3: Typical load-displacement diagrams of cyclic single-fiber push-back tests performed on pre-pushed fibers revealing abrupt (a) and progressive (b) failure behavior during push-out testing.

3.4 Evaluation of the interfacial fracture toughness

Cyclic single-fiber push-out tests were performed on the three samples of type C/PEEK with different thickness. For an overview of the samples investigated, see Table 1. The expanded energy analysis described in the present study, was applied to the push-out tests conducted. In Figure 4, the normalized energies dissipated by stable crack growth are shown as function of the three sample thicknesses examined. It can be seen that the points can be approximated by a linear regression intercepting the axis

of sample thickness at 6.3 μm . These push-out measurements confirm that there is both stable and unstable crack propagation involved in the debonding process, as it was verified in other push-out studies [7, 9]. The slope of the straight line corresponds to the interfacial fracture toughness $\langle G \rangle$, as described in Refs. [7, 9, 10]. For the composite specimen investigated, $\langle G \rangle$ amounts to $175 \pm 34 \text{ J/m}^2$. Comparable values in the range of $24 \pm 15 \text{ J/m}^2$ to $57 \pm 23 \text{ J/m}^2$, determined on a C/Polyphenylene sulfide (PPS) composite material, are reported in our previous work [9]. The interfacial fracture toughness of C/PEEK investigated in the present study is larger by a factor of 3-7 than the C/PPS composite.

Figure 4: Diagram of the normalized energy dissipated by stable crack growth during push-out testing as a function of sample thickness.

4 CONCLUSION

In the present publication, an expanded approach for quantification of the relevant energy dissipated in stable crack propagation during single-fiber push-out testing is presented.

The cyclic single-fiber push-out tests on C/PEEK revealed two different failure behaviors. Nearly half of the tests showed abrupt failure of the fiber-matrix bonding, whereas the other half of the tests failed progressively. The progressive push-out is attributed to high interfacial friction, which prevents an abrupt fiber relaxation towards the specimen back side at the moment of complete debonding. In case of progressive failure behavior, the energy analysis of the push-out tests revealed a deviation from linear behavior of the total plastic energy towards the end of the experiment. The linear increase is attributed to stable crack propagation and is characteristic for abrupt failure behavior. The deviation correlates to the onset of a stick-slip behavior, as verified by additional push-back testing of the pre-pushed fibers. Based on these findings, a new approach to determine the endpoint of stable crack growth is proposed. By applying this approach to the measured push-out tests, the linear relationship between the total energy dissipated during stable crack growth and the sample thickness has been verified experimentally. The length of unstable crack and the interfacial fracture toughness have been evaluated.

The results confirm that the extension of the method to quantify the relevant crack energy is applicable to composite materials comprising a high friction contribution along the fiber-matrix interface.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

The authors would like to thank the German Aerospace Center (DLR) in Stuttgart for kindly providing the thermoplastic composite.

REFERENCES

- [1] L.T. Drzal, The role of the fiber-matrix interphase on composite properties, *Vacuum*, **41(7-9)**, 1990, pp. 1615-1618.
- [2] D.A. Jesson, J.F. Watts, The interface and interphase in polymer matrix composites: effect on mechanical properties and methods for identification, *Polymer Reviews*, **52(3-4)**, 2012, pp. 321-354.
- [3] F.R. Jones, A review of interphase formation and design in fibre-reinforced composites, *Journal of Adhesion Science and Technology*, **24**, 2010, pp. 171-202.
- [4] R.J. Kerans, T.A. Parthasarathy, Theoretical analysis of the fiber pullout and pushout tests, *Journal of the American Ceramic Society*, **74(7)**, 1991, pp. 1585-1596.
- [5] T. Ramanathan, A. Bismarck, E. Schulz, K. Subramanian, Investigation of the influence of surface-activated carbon fibres on debonding energy and frictional stress in polymer-matrix composites by the micro-indentation technique, *Composites Science and Technology*, **61(16)**, 2001, pp. 2511-2518.
- [6] W.M. Mueller, J. Moosburger-Will, M.G.R. Sause and S. Horn, Microscopic analysis of single-fiber push-out tests on ceramic matrix composites performed with Berkovich and flat-end indenter and evaluation of interfacial fracture toughness, *Journal of the European Ceramic Society*, **33(2)**, 2013, pp. 441-451.
- [7] W.M. Mueller, J. Moosburger-Will, M.G.R. Sause, M. Greisel and S.Horn, Quantification of the crack area in ceramic matrix composites at single-fiber push-out testing and influence of pyrocarbon fiber coating thickness on interfacial fracture toughness, *accepted for publication in Journal of the European Ceramic Society*, 2015.
- [8] A. Battisti, D.E. los Ojos, R. Ghisleni and A.J. Brunner, Single fiber push-out characterization of interfacial properties of hierarchical CNT-carbon fiber composites prepared by electrophoretic deposition, *Composites Science and Technology*, **95**, 2014, pp. 121-127.
- [9] M. Greisel, J. Jäger, J. Moosburger-Will, M.G.R. Sause, W.M. Mueller and S. Horn, Influence of residual thermal stress in carbon fiber-reinforced thermoplastic composites on interfacial fracture toughness evaluated by cyclic single-fiber push-out tests, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **66**, 2014, pp. 117-127.
- [10] J. Jäger, M.G.R. Sause, F. Burkert, J. Moosburger-Will, M. Greisel and S. Horn, Influence of plastic deformation on single fiber push-out tests of carbon fiber reinforced epoxy resin, *Composites Part A: Applied Science and Manufacturing*, **71**, 2014, pp. 157-167.